

YouCount
Youth Citizen Science

D5.7

Continuous, updated DEC and stakeholder engagement plan, and report on DEC activities

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101005931

Project Acronym	YouCount
Project Name	YouCount – Empowering youth and cocreating social innovations and policymaking through youth-focused citizen social science
Grant Agreement no.	101005931
Start date of the project	01 / 02 / 2021
End date of the project	30/ 01 / 2024
Work Package producing the document	WP5
WP Leader	5, FD
Other Partners involved	2, VA; 1, OsloMet; 11, SPOTTERON
Deliverable identifier	5.7
Deliverable lead beneficiary	5, FD
Internal Scientific Reviewer	OsloMet- Aina Landsverk Hagen
Due date	31, May, 2021
Date of delivery	28, May, 2021
Version	5.0
Author(s)	5, FD; 2, VA; 1, OsloMet; 11, SPOTTERON
Classification	Public

Disclaimer: This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No101005931. The opinions expressed in this document reflect only the author’s view and reflects in no way the European Commission’s opinions. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Table of Contents

D5.7 CONTINUOUS, UPDATED DEC AND STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT PLAN, AND REPORT ON DEC ACTIVITIES	5
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	9
1 INTRODUCTION	11
2. PURPOSE AND SCOPE	12
3. OVERALL APPROACH TO DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION.....	12
4. MAIN STAKEHOLDER GROUPS	13
5. EXPLOITATION STRATEGY.....	15
6. DISSEMINATION STRATEGY.....	18
7. COMMUNICATION STRATEGY.....	22
7.1 Website and Project Identity.....	22
7.3. Leaflets	24
7.4. List of Planned Participation in Events	24
7.5. Newsletter and Press Releases.....	24
7.6. Non-Scientific Publications and Media Coverage	25
7.7. General Public Events.....	25
8. OPEN ACCESS PUBLICATIONS.....	27
9. PARTNER ROLES	27
10. MONITORING AND EVALUATION.....	28
11. EDITORIAL PLAN FOR THE WEBSITE AND SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS	29
12. ETHICS RELEVANCE	29
13. POST-PROJECT EXPLOITATION	30
APPENDIXES.....	32

List of figures

FIGURE 1: THE OVERALL APPROACH TO MAXIMISING IMPACT IN YOUCOUNT..... 13
FIGURE 2: RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH COMMUNICATION FOR Y-CSS..... 17

List of tables

TABLE 1: REVISION HISTORY..... 6
TABLE 2: TERMS AND ABBREVIATIONS..... 7
TABLE 3: MAIN STAKEHOLDER GROUPS AND EXPECTED AREAS OF INTEREST..... 14
TABLE 4: KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS..... 15
TABLE 5: FEATURES OF RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH COMMUNICATION FOR Y-CSS 17
TABLE 6: TARGETS FOR KEY DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES..... 19
TABLE 7: YOUCOUNT’S SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS..... 23
TABLE 8: TARGETS FOR KEY COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES..... 25
TABLE 9: APPENDIXES 32

D5.7 Continuous, updated DEC and stakeholder engagement plan, and report on DEC activities

Based on the overall strategy described in section 2.2. of the Document of Action (DoA), the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan will be developed to ensure stakeholder engagement at multiple levels. It will draw on the networks, communication channels and vehicles of the Partners represented in the consortium, aligning with the activities/events they organize, including the Advisory Board (AB) and European Citizen Science Association (ECSA). The countries/events of upcoming European Union (EU) presidencies will be targeted specifically. The plan also includes a strategy for engaging with and monitoring social media. The execution of the plan, as well as its implementation will be actively monitored and continuously updated to align with stakeholders needs and preferences throughout the project. At the end of the project, an updated DEC plan with a complete report on the activities will be provided. This task results in D5.7.

The vision of YouCount are twofold, addressing and combining both the scientific and societal needs of our time. The scientific vision of YouCount is to strengthen the transformative and participatory aspects of Citizen Science (CS) and social science, by enabling citizen participation in all facets, reaching out for a more egalitarian way of conducting science. The societal vision of YouCount is to contribute to create inclusive and innovative societies for European youths and to empower them in promoting active citizenship and a just and equitable future, particularly for youths from disadvantaged areas.

Table 1: Revision history

VERSION	DATE	CREATED BY	COMMENTS
1.0	16 / 04 / 2021	5, FD	First draft with structure and content
2.0	07/05/2021	5, FD	Version incorporating comments by VA, OsloMet and SPOTTERON.
3.0	21/05/2021	5, FD	Version incorporating comments and suggestions by internal scientific reviewer.
4.0	25/05/2021	5, FD	Version incorporating comments by members of the General Assembly
5.0	28/05/2021	P5, Patricia Canto Farachala	Final version submitted

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Cited as: Canto-Farachala P., Lorenz, U., Franco, S., Brounéus, F., Norvoll, R. and Hummer, P. *YouCount. D.5.7 Continuous, updated DEC and stakeholder engagement plan, and report on DEC activities*. Zenodo. doi.10.5281/zenodo.4812107

Table 2: Terms and Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	FULL TERM
AB	Advisory Board
BA	Bachelor of Arts
CS	Citizen Science
CSA	Citizen Science Associations
CSS	Citizen Social Science
D&E	Dissemination and Exploitation
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Document of Action
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
LL	Living Lab
MA	Master of Arts

MoRRI	Monitoring the Evolution and Benefits of Responsible Research and Innovation
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
RRC	Responsible Research Communication
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SwafS	Science with and for Society
WP	Work Package
YCS	Young citizen scientist
Y-CSS	Youth Citizen Social Science

Executive Summary

YouCount is an EU project funded under the Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society (SwafS) programme. Its main objective is to generate new knowledge and innovations to increase the social inclusion of youth at risk of exclusion across Europe through co-creative youth citizen social science (Y-CSS). YouCount's research design is organized in 6 different work packages (WP). WP5, which is closely interlinked with all the other WPs, aims to maximise the project's overall impact. This DEC plan is one of its main deliverables.

The strategy to maximise the overall impact of the project set out in this DEC plan responds to the recommendations by the European Commission (EC) to disseminate and to more effectively exploit publicly funded research results into socioeconomic benefits (EC, 2008). The DEC plan identifies the project's main stakeholder groups and describes the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities aimed at ensuring their engagement during the project and beyond it. The execution of the DEC plan will be monitored throughout the project, in order to draw lessons that improve its implementation. It is therefore a living document, likely to change throughout the life of the project.

Indeed, while maintaining its focus of contributing to maximise the overall impact of the project, the DEC plan will adapt and change, being responsive to lessons that emerge from reflecting on DEC practice. The YouCount proposal was drafted before the SARS-CoV-2 virus spread into a pandemic that resulted in the restriction of mobility, changing the way we interact with each other. The DEC plan, like the project, will need to navigate the changing circumstances that are likely to emerge from the context of uncertainty at the global and local levels thereby strengthening its applicability across a variety of contexts and unforeseen situations.

The project's overall approach to maximising impact is based on an integrated dissemination, exploitation and communication design that draws from the research team's tradition working with participatory methodologies. It addresses three different communication spaces situated at the micro, meso and macro levels.

The micro level is the space where dialogic communication will develop within 9 different living labs (LLs) across Europe. Through the LLs the project will explore how actual and meaningful dialogue can develop between youth and other (adult) stakeholders (policy makers, politicians, researchers, etc.) to address situations of exclusion experienced by youths in disadvantaged areas. The macro level is the space where the results of the LL's adopt a one-way communication approach in the form of publications or interaction in conferences, necessary to disseminate findings. The meso level is an intermediate space that complements the micro and the macro spaces for enhanced impact through hybrid (dialogic and non-dialogic) formulas that aim to maximise the impact of the project well beyond the publication of results, through toolkits, handbooks etc.

The DEC plan is inspired by several exploitation, communication and dissemination plans in H2020. We especially thank the EU projects Urban policy innovation to address inequality with and for future generations (Uplift); Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action (CoAct); and FIT4FOOD2030.

1 Introduction

YouCount's overarching objective is to generate new knowledge and innovations to increase the social inclusion of youth at risk of exclusion across Europe through co-creative youth citizen social science (Y-CSS). Nine co-creative Y-CSS case studies across Europe will provide increased knowledge of the positive drivers for social inclusion in general and specific knowledge and innovation in 3 dimensions of social inclusion, namely: social participation; connectedness and social belonging; and citizenship and rights.

The project also aims to contribute to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 10, 8 and 3 which refer to creating more inclusive societies, decent work and health and well-being for youths, respectively. It also aims to contribute to SDG 5 by generating gender-specific knowledge to create gender-tailored actions. The project will also support the overarching goal of the Science with and for Society (SwafS) programme by contributing to the Monitoring the Evolution and Benefits of Responsible Research and Innovation (MoRRI) indicators concerning science communication, public engagement and open access.

YouCount will achieve its objectives through a research design organized in 6 work packages (WPs): WP1 will focus on developing the framework and stakeholder mobilisation; WP2 will work on implementing the multiple case study; WP3 will perform an analysis of social inclusion and innovations; WP4 will develop the evaluation and impact assessment; WP5 will focus on dissemination, exploitation and communication; and, WP6 is on project management and ethics.

The main objective of WP5, which is closely interlinked with all the other WPs, is to maximise the project's overall impact by means of:

- **Designing and implementing effective and targeted dissemination strategies to enable the uptake of project outputs.**
- **Designing and implementing an effective and targeted communication strategy with multilevel stakeholder engagement (including the academic community) to support the mobilisation of a wide variety of actors.**
- **Designing and implementing an exploitation strategy to ensure the best possible use of YouCount results after the end of the EU-funded project.**

The DEC plan presented in this document is one of the deliverables from WP5.

2. Purpose and Scope

The DEC plan sets out a strategy to maximise the overall impact of the project, which can be summarised as follows: (i) to explore and support CS by expanding and developing CS in the social sciences (ii) to use co-creative Y-CSS for creating new knowledge and pushing ahead policy-making to increase the social inclusion of youth; (iii) to advance CS tools for science communication and public engagement in the social sciences particularly for youths from disadvantaged areas (iv) to integrate CS more actively in mainstream R&I institutions; and (v) to develop formal/informal science education in Citizen Social Science (CSS).

Moreover, it responds to the recommendation by the EC to disseminate and to more effectively exploit publicly-funded research results into socio-economic benefits (EC, 2008) and more specifically, to the requirements in Article 28 and 29 of the Grant Agreement (GA) on exploitation and dissemination of results. The former states that the project should take measures aiming to ensure exploitation of the project's results up to four years after the end of the project and the latter that the project's results need to be disseminated as soon as possible by disclosing them to the public, including scientific publications. Moreover, the Letter on Dissemination and Exploitation (D&E) obligations and opportunities beyond the end of the grant, strongly recommends that Key Exploitable Results (KERs) such as policy recommendations, should be published on the Horizon Results Platform¹.

3. Overall Approach to Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

The YouCount consortium is made up of research professionals working with participatory methodologies. Participatory research methodologies are based on dialogue, a powerful form of incorporating science communication in social change processes. However, dialogue between youth and other (adult) stakeholders is dependent on someone creating an equalizer effect (Tolstad et al. 2017), where the power differences are balanced as much as possible. Training the youth in research methods is one strategy for doing this. Moreover, when it comes to communication, youth interviewing journalists or communication advisors is another strategy for enabling actual and meaningful dialogue (Listerborn, 2007).

YouCount will work to maximise dialogue's transformation potential by adapting Responsible Research Communication (RRC) (Canto-Farachala, 2020) to its DEC strategy. RRC adds an intermediate layer between the micro space where dialogic face-to-face participatory research takes place and the macro space where research results are disseminated through one-way communication (i.e. distribution of printed or digital copies of research outputs, interaction in

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

conferences or seminars) and evaluated quantitatively (i.e. number of downloads, books, conferences). It complements the macro and micro spaces for enhanced impact through creative hybrid formulas that result in products such as toolkits and handbooks aimed at maximising the impact of the project well beyond the publication of results. These spaces do not exclude each other but complement and sometimes overlap with each other.

9

Figure 1: The overall approach to maximising impact in YouCount

The DEC plan is a living document that, while maintaining its focus of contributing to maximise the overall impact of the project, will adapt and change as the project develops, being responsive to lessons that emerge from reflecting on DEC practice. Moreover, the YouCount proposal was drafted before the SARS-CoV-2 virus spread into a pandemic that resulted in the restriction of mobility, bringing interaction to digital platforms. The DEC plan, like the project, will need to navigate the changing circumstances that are likely to emerge from the context of uncertainty at the global and local levels and will by this strengthen its applicability across a huge variety of contexts and situations of the unforeseen.

4. Main Stakeholder Groups

In order to achieve the impact objectives of YouCount, the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities will initially target 8 main stakeholder groups. Table 3 presents said groups and their expected key areas of interest.

Table 3: Main stakeholder groups and expected areas of interest

Stakeholder group	Expected key areas of interest
Academic community	How to plan, conduct and evaluate high-quality Y-CSS
Mutual learning processes with CS projects in the call (SwafS)	How to conduct and evaluate high-quality Y-CSS for youths from disadvantaged areas and increase the transformative potential of CS?
Research councils and organisations interested in science communication	How to conduct and evaluate high-quality Y-CSS and develop targeted CS policy
Research councils and organisations interested in science communication	How could social science become an influential knowledge provider/force for driving knowledge production in CS/CSS?
University institutions (formal education)	How to teach CSS in universities
Policy-makers and community stakeholders, employers and end user organisations	How to use CSS and youth-involved CS as a way of informing policy/development/planning and increasing the community’s capacity to deal with societal challenges relevant to their context. Substantial topic knowledge (youth employment, discrimination, etc.)
Young people	How can CSS help me identify my passions and/or achieve my goals in life?
General public	How can CSS help to strengthen our communities, and Y-CSS enable youth to become socially included on their own terms?

5. Exploitation Strategy

The YouCount research team understands exploitation as the measures designed to enable the uptake of the project’s results beyond the life of the project. Its objectives are (i) to mobilise a wide group of experts and stakeholders on all levels; (ii) to develop and expand CSS in the social sciences; (iii) to contribute to strengthen R&I policy concerning CS, specifically CSS; (iv) to provide hands-on future-oriented training concerning CS in the social sciences and; (v) to build competencies among academic and societal actors on CSS. Its key exploitable results are described in the project’s Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) plan (Deliverable 6.3) and listed in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Key exploitable results

Key exploitable results	Target stakeholders	Exploitation route
Communication and collaboration structures between R&I institutions and society	Universities and municipalities and regions	Use CS to develop co-creative projects and proposals together with municipalities and regions to support bottom-up policies and innovations. Using the resources in R&I institutions to support society in knowledge development
Social innovations resulting from case studies	Local and national stakeholders participating in case studies	Development of local case studies (LLs and national workshops)
Formal education modules and programmes	Universities	Scientific publications and about 18 students in social work, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), communication, sociology or similar will write their Master of Arts (MA) or Bachelor of Arts (BA) theses from the project findings, supporting the integration of CS in traditional formal education
Science communication institutions collaboration	Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) /science communication organisations, etc.	Foundation Deusto and Vetenskap & Allmänhet with their expertise in science communication will use their networks and contribute to publish at least one article

		concerning science communication/public engagement of youths in science together with the consortium
Policy recommendations for future CS	Local to European policy-makers and interest groups (European Youth council, Youth Alliance for Leadership and Development in Africa, etc.)	General and country-specific policy briefs and recommendations
Scientific guidelines and recommendations	Academics, research councils and CS-organisations	These results will be disseminated to the stakeholders, who will also participate in the AB at the national/European level
ICT tools	ICT-units at R&I institutions, youth, schools and universities and on the private market	In collaboration with youth and researchers in the YouCount project, SPOTTERON will create new features of ICT tools for CS
Capacity building and policy alignment in Europe concerning CSS	CS-organisations, networks and related CS-projects at the national and European levels	Through collaboration with other CS-projects, networks, Citizen Science Associations (CSA) and COST actions
Handbook and Toolkits for Y-CSS	All stakeholders	Disseminated and communicated through homepages, universities, NGO/science communication Partners linking up to CS-organisations/CSA (e.g. ECSA), CS-networks and other stakeholders
Website for Y-CSS	All stakeholders including youth and the general public	The homepage will exist for at least 3 years. It will be linked to CS-organisations, consortium and participating stakeholder institutions and disseminated through media, youth and community networks and schools

All the results of the project will be publicly available and will follow an integrated RRC design for Y-CSS to maximise their exploitation. Moreover, consortium Partners and the participating youth will proactively engage with stakeholders interested in using YouCount. The project results will also be exploited by the consortium members.

Source: Adapted from Canto-Farachala (2020); Brown, C. et al. (2019); Vestby, N. (2020).

Figure 2: Responsible Research Communication for Y-CSS

The description of each feature is shown in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Features of Responsible Research Communication for Y-CSS

Feature	Description
Change-oriented	The design of each exploitable result will be guided by an objective jointly identified through dialogue with youth and other target groups.
Smart	Deferred: A deferred dialogue is a written dialogue that takes place delayed in time between researchers and youths sharing a specific research output and other

	<p>researchers and youths who could have interest in said research output. A deferred dialogue needs <i>ex-ante</i> facilitation, designed with a heightened awareness of the need to reduce barriers that may emerge from participants' different contexts, profiles, backgrounds, disciplines...</p>
	<p>Emergent:</p> <p>An emergent dialogue is dynamic, ongoing and changing, unfolding step by step, facilitated <i>in situ</i> by the researchers and youths communicating a research output or by participating researchers, youths or practitioners. It may take different forms (virtual, non-virtual...).</p>
Inclusive	<p>It is open and inclusive of the views, reflections, approaches, knowledge and perspectives originally excluded from the research output that is being communicated. It is perceived as meaningful and relevant to the participants and communicated with empathy and respect for difference.</p>
Sensuous	<p>Words are not always what helps youths communicate best and other ways of experiencing and expressing knowing need to be considered, including the tactile, audible and visual.</p>
Collective	<p>Keeping the dialogue alive is a collective responsibility and depends on the extent to which participants find their participation valuable and meaningful for them.</p>

Source: Adapted from Canto-Farachala; Brown, C. et al. (2019); Vestby, N. (2020).

6. Dissemination Strategy

The YouCount research team understands dissemination as making available the results of the project as soon as possible to a diverse set of stakeholders. It supports exploitation and is supported by communication activities. Its main objective is to engage key citizen scientists and other stakeholders at the local, national and global levels to facilitate the scaling up of the project's main findings. Table 6 lists the type of dissemination activities, their main target groups and a detailed description of the journals and conferences that have been so far been identified by Partners as potential dissemination spaces.

Table 6: Targets for key dissemination activities

Type of activities	Target groups	Detailed description
Publications	Academic Community (N=13)	<p>Scientific Publications in high-impact, peer reviewed journals in the social sciences, social and community psychology, communication and ICT and related to substantial topics</p> <p><i>Action Research Journal; American Journal of Community Psychology; Children and Youth Services Review; Citizenship Studies; Community Psychology in a Global Perspective; International Journal of Action Research; International Journal of Communication; International Journal of Social Research Methodology; International Journal of Social Work; JCOM; Journal of Community and Applied Social Psychology; Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies; Journal of Participatory Research; Journal of Social Policy; Journal of Youth and Adolescence; Nature; Palgrave Communications; Participatory Educational Research; PLOS One; Policy & Society; Research for All; Sage Open Media and Communication; Social inclusion; Social Issues and Policy Review; Sociological Methods and Research; Sociology; Universal Access in the Information Society; Urban Policy and Research; Urban Studies; Work, Employment and Society; Youth and Society.</i></p>

	Academic community and practitioners (N=3)	Publications in CS organisations' journals like <i>Citizen Science, Theory and Practice</i>
	Research councils, employment services, professionals working with youth and migrants and social work/policy in the national and European setting	Scientific or popular science publications co-written with Young citizen scientists (YCS) and short letters/news in targeted policy and professional journals.
Presentations	National and international conferences for the academic community in communication, sociology, social anthropology, social and community psychology, and social policy (N=22)	American Anthropology Association (AAA) Annual Meeting; METROPOLIS EURA of the European Urban Research Association; International Association for Media and Communication Research (IAMCR); and Computer Human Interaction (CHI); International Conference on Social, Economic and Cultural Transformations (2021 Oslo); European Federation of Psychologists' Associations (EFPA, 2022, Ljubjiana); European Community Psychology Conference (ECPA, 2023); International Conference on Community Psychology (ICCP, 2022, Naples); National Conference on Community Psychology (SIPCO, 2023); EuroChild and youth participation conferences as well as those that target migrants, citizenship, social inclusion and employability and social innovation.
	Research council conferences/workshops and national policy conferences/meetings	Participation in at least one conference arranged by the research councils in each country and presentation of YouCount results in

		one policy conference meeting in each country
Scientific sessions	Academic community (N=2)	Participation in the ECSA conference to present the YouCount project, participation in another relevant social science conference organising a scientific session
Website and bi-annual e-newsletter	All stakeholders, youth and the general public	Continuous dissemination of project activities, reports and other outputs like news, updates and information
Social media dialogue	All stakeholders, youth and the general public	Social media channels: Initially Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, YouTube, Snapchat and others identified with YCS
European and national policy briefs on Y-CSS	Policy makers and organisations interested in CSS	Briefs on CSS, recommendations on CSS implementation policy and social inclusion of youth
National workshops	Academic community and stakeholder groups	One in each country to present results, organized by Partners
Integration in formal education	Universities	Lectures on CSS and YouCount in relevant teaching courses and BA, MA and PhD level in science education and social policy/communication/ICT
LLs, trainings and forums	Local youths, stakeholders and policy makers	The results of the project will be made available to participants in the case studies on an ongoing basis
YouCount final conference	Policy makers at the European and local levels	A final conference will be organised at the end of the project in Brussels to present the results of the project

The list of planned participation in events will be updated and followed up according to deliverable D.5.6: List of planned participation in events.

7. Communication Strategy

Communication activities refer to all activities that aim to inform and promote the project activities on a continuous basis to multiple audiences, looking specifically to engage with the project multilevel platform and to carry out targeted communication with the stakeholders to mobilise and retain their involvement in CS in the social sciences. The youth and the researchers will participate in the design of the different tools to carry out the project communication activities from the early stages.

7.1 Website and Project Identity

Central to all communication actions is the YouCount public project website. The website will be developed within six months of the project. The creation of the website and the project identity itself will include the participation of the YCS who are already active in some of the country cases and it will continue to incorporate their inputs and views throughout the life of the project. It will be maintained by SPOTTERON during the project period. The project website and identity are described in deliverable D5.1/D12. Some of its main features are the following:

- **The website will provide information about the consortium Partners, objectives of the project, phases and outcomes.**
- **It will announce all the events of the YouCount consortium well in advance to allow for interested persons to sign up, learn about the project and meet project Partners.**
- **It will include a Blog through which researchers, the early career research group and YCS will share stories, news and reflections on the different cases (see section 11).**
- **It will become a connecting space for persons interested in the project and create a community of interest in Y-CSS through a specific space where people can sign up.**

Like the DEC plan, the website will change and adapt, reflecting the development of the project.

The website's URL is: <https://www.youcountproject.eu>

7.2 Social Media Channels

Social media will be used to engage with different stakeholders at the international, European and local levels, creating awareness of the need to address the risk of social exclusion faced by substantial numbers of young people in Europe and globally and how social citizen science can contribute to address this social challenge.

The YouCount project will initially use Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat and YouTube as its main social media channels. However, apart from Twitter and Facebook, the choice of social media channels will be made when the Partners start working with the youths in the country cases. This aims to guarantee that the project uses the ones that work best for them and represent them.

The social media channels will specifically work on three levels:

- **To broadcast news, stories and information on YouCount events and publications.**
- **To engage different stakeholders in dialogue in order to obtain their input, views and insight on the project, particularly young people.**
- **To identify new stakeholders and people interested in the project.**

An Editorial Plan (see section 11), describes the guidelines and procedures related to the use of the social media channels in the project. Table 7 lists the channels and handles created so far.

Table 7: YouCount’s social media channels

Social Media Channel	Handle
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/youcountproject/
Twitter	@youcountproject
Instagram	
LinkedIn	
YouTube	

In line with the DEC plan, which is a living document that will adapt and change as the project develops, the use of one or another channel will also be responsive to lessons that emerge from practice. In any case, YouCount social media channels will be complemented by each Partner, who will use language specific channels to make sure that YouCount is present in their own languages, adapted to their particular context.

The main hashtag for the project is #youcountproject. This main hashtag is complemented with two additional lists of hashtags that will be adapted along the way as we learn what works best. The first one is meant to target stakeholders and projects at the European level, and the second one to target young people.

- **The initial list of hashtags for stakeholders at the European level: #CitizenSocialScience; #CitSci, #SwafS, #youth; #Social Inclusion**
- **The second list that represents and speaks to the young people will be defined as soon as work with them begins in the local cases**

7.3. Leaflets

During the life of the project, two leaflets will be developed: one in month 6 and the other one in month 34. The first one will present the project objectives and the second one will present the project results. The Partners will distribute printed copies of the leaflets in their own countries to increase the project's visibility, particularly among stakeholders who are not active in social media or directly involved in the project. This way they have something tangible that leads them to more information about the project.

7.4. List of Planned Participation in Events

The List of Planned participation in events (D. 5.6) is due by July 30th, 2021. It will set the ground by which the consortium members plan and report on the events as defined in the DoA. It will keep track of the events that are taking place as part of the project and will provide updates on the coverage of the commitments with the EC regarding event participation.

7.5. Newsletter and Press Releases

Bi-annual e-newsletters will be sent to different stakeholder groups. Press releases will be published at regular intervals, for example, when key results have been achieved or before project events, to attract media attention and news coverage.

7.6. Non-Scientific Publications and Media Coverage

Existing contacts with journalists and the abovementioned press releases will be used to generate mass media coverage of the project. In the past, the activities of the consortium Partners have been covered by newspapers, magazines, radio and TV programmes at the national level and podcasts made at the universities. Partners will strive to receive mass media coverage on the project at least once during the life of the project.

7.7. General Public Events

The project will be presented in at least 11 events targeting the general public, particularly young people. The focus will be on events aiming at popularising science for a broad audience, for example, the annual days for research on national levels (Norway), Science Friday (Sweden), Social Science Festival (the UK) and open door days of the project Partners.

All YouCount events will ensure diversity of experiences and viewpoints. In all its events:

- **People under 30 will make up at least 25% of all speakers**
- **Women and men will be equally represented as speakers**

Table 8: Targets for key communication activities

Channel	Audience	Impact	Evaluation
Website	All stakeholders	Awareness and promotion of the project engagement	Number of project consultations, total clicks: 3000
Leaflets	All stakeholders	Awareness and promotion of the project engagement	Number of copies distributed: printed version 900
eNewsletters	All stakeholders, contact data base of project Partners	Awareness and promotion of the project engagement	Number of recipients ~20 000 (all partner contacts)
Press releases	All stakeholders	Awareness and promotion of the project	36 press releases

Media coverage	All stakeholders	Awareness and promotion of the project	Number of mentions of YouCount project in the media
Non-scientific publications	All stakeholders, especially the general public	Promotion of the project	Number of subscribers of magazines
Videos (YouTube channel)	All stakeholders	Promotion of the project	~700-1500 viewers
Podcasts	All stakeholders	Promotion of the project	Number of downloads
General public events	Citizens, students, children, families	Promotion of the project	~11 events Number of participants from different target groups
Social media	All stakeholders and general public	Awareness of and engagement with the project	Number of followers Number of shares Number of replies Number of discussions developed
In-App Social Features / User Community	All stakeholders, all participants	Ongoing active community, motivation, exchange / e-learning by participant	Number of in-App comments Number of contributions
External content sharing	All stakeholders, all participants	Dissemination of public in-App contributions in external social media by users	N/A

8. Open Access Publications

Following its Open Science profile, the project's results will be published in open access sources: scientific journals, and public EU deliverables and other kinds of publications in the open repository Zenodo linked to Open Aire. It will also store samples of open data in Zenodo, thereby aiming to be as "open as possible and as closed as necessary".

The project will develop an overarching publication policy aiming to publish in high-quality open access journals in the social sciences and related disciplines. Some of the journals that have been identified by partners are *Sage Open*, *Media and Communication* and *International Journal of Communication*. This is important for increasing the scientific 'reputation' of CS in traditional science. The opportunities for publishing in 'gold open access' are partly included in the budget in combination with archiving the publication in a repository at the time of submission (self-archiving 'green open science'). In addition, each partner will ensure open access to all publications relating to its results, free of charge. Moreover, open science will be in line with the requirements and legitimate claims to protect (exploitation), confidentiality (personal data) and security as explained in the GA and the deliverables IPR plan and Data Management Plan (DMP).

Likewise, as explained in section 2, key exploitable results from the YouCount project will be published in the publishing platform recently launched by the EC Open Research Europe. The platform is meant to host scientific articles that present the results of research funded by Horizon 2020 (soon Horizon Europe).

9. Partner Roles

All Partners are DEC agents. They will use their local and national role and network to maximise the dissemination and exploitation of the project. Using their own channels and their local languages will ensure local communities have access to the knowledge produced in the project, contributing to maximise its outreach. Most Partners are closely involved in the development of the multiple case studies and their evaluation, which constitute the basis for the exploitable results of the project and their design. Appendix B presents a detailed inventory of the partner's communication tools and channels. More specific roles are:

- **FD/Orkestra will provide guidance and RRC expertise to all project Partners during the life of the project and will arrange a workshop to that end in 2021.**
- **SPOTTERON will create and manage the website and will create the YouCount social media channels, and train a group made up of one person from each partner on how to use the website content manager.**

- **All Partners will provide content for the website and feed the social media channels (see section 11).**
- **OsloMet will upload information on the website on project level, cross-cutting activities.**
- **All Partners will upload information on the website about the development of their case studies.**
- **Early career researchers and young citizen scientists will be encouraged to write posts for the website.**

Moreover, considering the cross-cutting nature of the DEC activities, all Partners will appoint one person as a communication contact to conform a team that will jointly address DEC-related issues as above and as needed.

10. Monitoring and Evaluation

In order to monitor the effectiveness of the project's DEC activities, quantitative indicators will be collected and monitored and qualitative investigations with target stakeholder groups will be developed. Partners will keep track of all YouCount DEC activities (other than standard social media and website interaction) in a shared template that will be used for both monitoring and periodic reporting on DEC activities. The template will develop from the List of Planned Participation in Events (Deliverable D. 5.6) to incorporate said DEC activities in an Excel sheet and shared with all Partners in Teams. When YouCount Partners carry out a specific action (i.e. press release, article, social media post, publication in their newsletter or website, participation in workshops, writing scientific articles, etc.) a new entry on the Excel log will be added including some basic information about the action and lessons learnt.

Visits to the website will be monitored by SPOTTERON to track user interaction, which topics people find more or less interesting, etc.

The YouCount social media channels will also provide important feedback on stakeholder engagement, particularly number of followers and interactions.

Participation in YouCount events, both physical and digital, will require the approval of participants, by signing a consent form. The number of participants can be monitored in this way.

11. Editorial Plan for the Website and Social Media Channels

Researchers, early career researchers and YCS will contribute content to the website. The social media channels will be linked to the website. They will have two main levels of content:

- **Project level: cross cutting issues such as project events and meetings, publications, news from the advisory board, connection with other SwafS CS projects, etc.**
- **Case level: development of the case studies in the different countries.**

The main source of content for the social media will be the news, stories, reflections and information that will be uploaded on the website by Partners. As stated in section 9 above, each partner will appoint one person to do so, having been trained to use the website content manager.

- **In order to guarantee social media presence throughout the life of the project, the consortium should upload at least 10 new items a month (one each per month).**
- **Each partner will upload their own content on the website.**
- **The website will incorporate a feature through which the content is automatically transferred to the social media channels.**
- **The partner uploading the content will be responsible for answering and following through engagement with stakeholders and followers.**
- **The content tone and voice should be including and inviting, using direct and clear language.**
- **Before posting, Partners should make sure that the content is readable, understandable and shareable; that the spelling and grammar is correct and that the text has no typos.**

12. Ethics Relevance

Any considerations relating to the use of data deriving from any monitoring and evaluation methods will require a rigorous ethics screening. The ethics requirements and procedures to guarantee a good balance between open data and confidentiality are described in the forthcoming

DMP, a deliverable due on July 2021. Both the IPR plan and the Project Execution Handbook elaborate on how this is envisioned in the ethical framework and data management. These requirements will apply to any type of data, be it statistical data or public user contributions, such as comments or likes, from the project's social media channels.

Personal data in terms of the use of videos and photos of participants, as well as quotes, job titles, correspondence address, geo-spatial information, among other, need to align with the practices set out in the Project Execution Handbook and data protection /ethics requirements for the project. All personal information as well as newsletter and internet list of stakeholders will be handled according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

13. Post-Project Exploitation

As mentioned in section 2, the exploitable results from the YouCount project will be shared openly in the form of Open Deliverable. This will be the case for the Tool-box for Y-CSS, the Handbook for Y-CSS and the two policy briefs. Similarly, the IT application will be based on open source software and made available under the appropriate open license and available in public repositories. Moreover, as explained in section 2, the project will take measures aiming to ensure exploitation of the project's results up to four years after the end of the project.

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Appendixes

Table 9: Appendixes

APPENDIX	SUBJECT	PAGE
Appendix A	Preliminary plan of communication activity	33
Appendix B	Inventory of Project partner's communication tools and channels	34

Appendix A. Preliminary Plan of Communication Activity

Activity	2021				2022			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Website		M4	Continuously					
Leaflets			M6					
eNewsletters			M6		M12		M18	
Press releases					M12			
Videos in YouTube channel							M18	
Non-scientific publications					M12			
General public events	Continuously							
Social media	Continuously							

Activity	2023				2024			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Website	Continuously							
Leaflets								
eNewsletters	M24		M30		M36			
Press releases	M24				M36			
Videos in YouTube channel			M30					
Non-scientific publications								
General public events	Continuously							
Social media	Continuously							

Appendix B. Inventory of Project Partner's Communication Tools and Channels

Partner/ contact	Website	Twitter	Linkedin	YouTube	Facebook	Instagram
OsloMet/AFI		@OsloMet	https://www.linkedin.com/school/oslomet/mycompany/	https://www.youtube.com/c/OsloMetFilm/featured	https://www.facebook.com/oslomet ,	
AFI		@AFI_forskning			https://www.facebook.com/AFIforskning	
VA	https://v-a.se	@vetenskapollm	https://www.linkedin.com/company/vetenskapollm	https://www.youtube.com/user/vetenskapollmanhet	https://www.facebook.com/vetenskapollm	https://www.instagram.com/vetenskapollm
SH	https://www.sh.se/english/sodertorn-university				https://www.sh.se/english/sodertorn-university	
UCLan	www.uclan.ac.uk	@UCLan	https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-central-lancashire/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCzAuczZHeat2cm8E2Xf2e3g	@OfficialUCLan	@uclanuni
FD/Orkestra	https://www.orkestra.deusto.es/es/	@Orkestra	https://www.linkedin.com/company/orkestra-basque-institute-of-competitiveness/mycompany/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwmbDDFEzX1Dg37jSz-Bi3g		

UNIVIE	https://www.univie.ac.at/	@univienna	https://www.linkedin.com/school/univiennea/mycompany/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCghuDKOKiOCBdKffCtmE4A	https://www.facebook.com/univienna	@univienna
UNIVIE – department of communication	https://publizistik.univie.ac.at/	@IPKW_univie				
UNIVIE – Advertising and Media Effects (AdMe) Research Group	https://advertisingresearch.univie.ac.at/	@AdME_univie				
KTU	https://en.ktu.edu	@ktuspace	https://www.linkedin.com/school/ktu/mycompany/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCW6dwTSBsJ7StROHVdzPTQQ	https://lt.facebook.com/ktu.lt/	https://www.instagram.com/ktuspace/?hl=en
AAU	https://www.en.aau.dk/					
ESSRG	https://www.essrg.hu/en/	@essrg	https://www.linkedin.com/company/essrg/mycompany/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCFDDuxh_SvRZnf5QuvEICfw		
UNINA	https://www.unina.it	@UninaIT	https://www.linkedin.com/school/unina/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC8Q7t0_xrwnWauMOP-QCjtg	https://www.facebook.com/unina.it/	https://www.instagram.com/uninaait/

UNINA/Department	http://studiumanistici.dip.unina.it/					
SPOTTERON	https://www.spotteron.net	@spotteron		https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCmJAKl-nh62ku3JL6xY00tA	https://www.facebook.com/spotteron	https://www.instagram.com/spotteron/

YouCount

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